

How a sufficient sized moon is crucial to maintaining the existence of an atmosphere on the planet which that moon orbits.

By Eamonn Trainor – Dated: May 7, 2018

Our solar system has 3 planets in the “goldilocks zone” or zone of habitability around our star, the Sun. They are Venus, Earth and Mars.

However, neither Mars or Venus are conducive to life – as Venus is too hot, and Mars is too cold. Earth is in the middle of the habitable zone while Venus and Mars are outliers in the zone of habitability.

Venus may have once had a more Earth like environment but fell prey to the runaway greenhouse effect probably because it was too close to the Sun and subject to higher concentration of solar heating through radiation. This created a feed back loop and gradually increased the density of the atmosphere and the environmental heat due to a build up of gases which could not escape its atmosphere.

Mars is too far away from the Sun to receive sufficient solar heating radiation and is indeed very cold except at some short mid-day times near the equator in the Martian summer. Otherwise, Mars is far colder than Antarctica for all other times and regions.

In addition, neither Venus or Mars have magnetic fields. Magnetic fields are crucially important in two respects.

Firstly, they will help shield a planet from too much solar or cosmic radiation and this could have beneficial effects on organic life evolving, although some radiation helps mutation and therefore diversity and in turn helps drive the forces of evolution. Generally, radiation is bad for life as it causes the breakdown of cells.

Secondly, and far more importantly, a magnetic field will shield the atmosphere of a planet from the dissipating effects of solar wind/radiation and cosmic radiation. Without a magnetic field, a planet will be stripped of its atmosphere eventually with devastating effects on any life on that planet. The pressure of the solar wind on any sufficiently close in atmosphere will tend to blow off that atmosphere over time This is most probably what happened on Mars. Mars has a very thin atmosphere which has been stripped away over millennia by the solar wind from our Sun and cosmic radiation hitting the molecules in its atmosphere and breaking them apart which in turn causes them to be too light to be retained by Mar’s low gravity and they fly off into space.

The Earth’s Moon has been very fortuitous for life on Earth mainly due to its size in comparison to the Earth. The moon stabilizes our spin (we don’t wobble so much), has slowed down our spin to dampen strong winds, maintains our seasons by through the tilt of the Earth but, most importantly of all, it keeps active the inner molten iron mantle of the Earth through gravitational tidal pulling on the molten mantle due to the size of the

Moon compared to the Earth. That is, the Moon is big enough to produce sufficient gravitational pulling forces on the Earth to cause the molten mantle to churn. When you have liquid iron moving, you create a magnetic field. This is how our Earth has a magnetic field.

Our Moon then, in effect, preserves our magnetic field. It helps perpetuate the churning or movement of the liquid (molten) iron mantle which needs to move to produce the magnetic field of the Earth. That magnetic field loops to and from each pole of our planet and creates field lines surrounding the exterior of the Earth's surface. The field lines are most closely congregated at the poles as they return to the interior of our planet. We see auroras at the poles due to the solar and cosmic radiation being able to get closer to the surface of the Earth. However, the magnetic field lines span above all layers of our atmosphere and they protect the layers of our atmosphere accordingly. That is, they deflect the charged particles from our Sun and extra-solar cosmic rays along the field lines and prevent them from colliding with our upper atmosphere. This is why we have the Van Allen belts or areas of high radiation density at certain regions orbiting the Earth. If the solar wind charges particles and cosmic were not deflected by Earth's magnetic shield, then the atmosphere of the Earth would be broken down by firstly the upper molecules of our atmosphere being subject to high velocity collisions by charged particles which will break apart the atmospheric molecules. Such breaking apart of molecules in the, at first, upper atmosphere, will send the consistent molecular parts into space directly due to the speed of the collisions imparting high velocity motion to the now smaller constituent parts of the former molecules or the gradual weakening of the layer of atmospheric molecules, so that they gradually leave Earth's gravity by floating off into space due to Earth's gravity not being able to hold onto the less dense particles. Over time, the earth's atmosphere would break down until it has very little, if eventually, or any atmosphere. This would have grave consequences for any life on Earth.

A churning molten mantle also causes our plate tectonics, volcanoes to erupt, as well as our magnetic field to stay strong. All these effects are beneficial to encouraging and preserving the existence of life on Earth. There are other effects from the tidal pulling of the moon on the Earth such as tides being produced in the oceans. The tidal effects will work on any liquid be it water or molten iron inside the Earth.

The Earth's Moon maintains the existence of the magnetic field of the Earth, which magnetic field, in turn, most crucially, protects our atmosphere from solar and cosmic radiation colliding with our atmosphere and thereby causing the dissipation of atmospheric molecules from our atmosphere into space and away from Earth's gravity well.

Venus may have acquired its super dense atmosphere while it had a magnetic field. Venus then fell victim to a runaway greenhouse effect. The runaway greenhouse effect was probably caused, substantially, by being closer to the Sun and having more heat hit its surface. The heating atmosphere became suffused with greenhouse and other

gases, which build-up was probably aided by the early magnetic field shielding Venus from solar and cosmic radiation which would otherwise break down the atmosphere and dissipate it off into space. Once the inner molten iron mantle of Venus cooled off and the molten metal solidified, it then lost its magnetic field. If Venus had had a moon of comparable size to the Earth's Moon, then its magnetic field might still be in existence today.

Venus still retains its ultra-dense atmosphere because of the prior build-up of the runaway greenhouse effect which increased atmospheric density to produce crushing pressure as you travel towards the surface and scorching heat due to the trapped gases. The upper atmosphere (ionosphere) still also acts in a way to repel solar radiation and the current density of the atmosphere helps prevent deep penetration by the solar wind. However, Venus is losing atmosphere to space, although it has a lot of atmosphere to lose. Venus will retain its thicker atmosphere longer than Mars but at a price of having its surface under crushing atmospheric pressure, toxic gases (Sulphuric acid) and incredible heat. However, Venus will eventually have its atmosphere removed by the solar wind and cosmic radiation.

Why did Venus lose its molten subterranean mantle? It was because it did not have a moon of comparable size to the Earth's moon. Over time, there was no continuing tidal pressure to cause any molten iron to continue to move. Without a comparable moon of sufficient proportionate mass to Earth's moon (Venus and Earth being almost identical in size) then there were no forces acting on any inner molten metal mantle to cause such molten mantle to continue or perhaps even begin to flow. Venus has a very low rate of spin as well, which would not have assisted in causing any churning motion to any inner molten mantle. Eventually, any molten mantle stopped all movement (perhaps it never even began) and it may have substantially solidified. Even if it has not solidified there would be no movement of molten iron to produce the necessary magnetic field. Therefore, Venus's magnetic field either switched off or never got started.

Mars was too small to begin with (one third the size of the Earth) and once again had no moon comparable in proportionate size of planet to moon as the Earth has with its Moon. Thus, once again, without a moon of big enough size to produce sufficient gravitational pulling, any molten iron would have ceased to move, and any magnetic field lost. Mars may also have been too small in size to perpetuate movement in an inner molten mantle to produce a magnetic field.

By the leading theory of the formation of our Moon, it seems probable that the Moon was created by the collision of a Mars size object with the early Earth. That billiard ball occurrence was very fortuitous for the early basic geologic and orbital conditions to, at least, not prevent the later biological and environmental conditions that eventually lead to the development of a life conducive environment on the Earth as discussed above.

The fortuitous event, of a collision of a large planetoid with a rocky planet, early in that planet's creation, in the eventual goldilocks zone of a star, to create a large moon for

that planet, may not happen much in other solar systems creation processes. This factor must be taken into account in any calculation of the statistical probability of other Earth like planets existing elsewhere in our galaxy.

The thesis of this paper is that:

A moon of sufficient size and/or density is necessary to maintain the magnetic field of any planet which it orbits.

Such magnetic field on any such planet, is crucial to maintaining the continued existence of an atmosphere for said planet.